

PREVALENCE AND PREDICTORS OF DEMEANING BEHAVIORS AMONG JUNIOR-RANKING POLICE OFFICERS IN OYO AREA COMMAND, NIGERIA*

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Abstract

Purpose: This study investigated the prevalence and predictors of demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers in Oyo, a semi-urban Nigerian policing context. While policing literature often frames officers as perpetrators of aggression toward citizens, little attention has been given to toxic workplace dynamics within the force itself. Design/Methodology: A cross-sectional survey was conducted with 100 junior-ranking officers selected from six divisions under Oyo Area Command. Standardized scales measured demeaning behaviors, occupational stress, authoritarian leadership, perceived organizational injustice, and ethical leadership. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression. Findings: Results revealed a high prevalence of demeaning behaviors, with 72% of officers reporting frequent experiences. Occupational stress ($\beta = .42, p < .001$) and perceived organizational injustice ($\beta = .37, p < .001$) significantly predicted demeaning behaviors. In contrast, authoritarian leadership ($\beta = .10, p = .270$) and ethical leadership ($\beta = -.08, p = .344$) were non-significant predictors. Practical Implications: The findings emphasize the urgent need for reforms in welfare, staffing ratios, and fairness mechanisms in the Nigerian Police Force. Addressing structural and organizational stressors is essential to reducing toxic peer interactions. Originality/Value: By shifting the focus from police as perpetrators toward internal workplace dynamics, this study fills a critical gap in organizational and policing

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scholarship. It demonstrates how stress and injustice, more than leadership style, explain the prevalence of demeaning behaviors in semi-urban Nigerian policing.

Key words: *Demeaning behavior, Police officers, Organizational injustice, Authoritarian leadership, Ethical leadership.*

1. Introduction

Demeaning behaviors at work, encompassing incivility, bullying, and abusive supervision, represent a spectrum of negative interpersonal interactions that have attracted growing scholarly attention (Schilpzand et al., 2016; Han et al., 2022; Vasconcelos, 2020). These behaviors produce significant personal costs, including elevated turnover intentions, diminished morale, and serious mental health consequences such as depression, anxiety, emotional burnout, and sleep disorders (Carter & Loh, 2017; Durmuş et al., 2024; Han et al., 2022), while organizations bear systemic losses in productivity, teamwork, and commitment (Rasool et al., 2013; Vasconcelos, 2020). High-stress professions such as healthcare, education, and law enforcement show heightened vulnerability to such mistreatment, though their internal relational dynamics remain underexplored (Martin & Zadinsky, 2022; Davis et al., 2024; Gershon et al., 2009). The workplace environment of policing is especially prone to demeaning conduct due to its hierarchical, militarized structure and authoritarian command culture (Shane, 2019; Jiang et al., 2017). Officers are conventionally framed as perpetrators of aggression toward citizens, obscuring the reality that junior-ranking officers are themselves often subjected to demeaning conduct within the force (Moffette & Bruckert, 2023; Adegbite & Atunwa, 2025; Yunusa & Usman, 2022). Despite organizational psychology widely acknowledging workplace incivility, its unique manifestation in policing remains understudied, risking the misrepresentation of internal police aggression as purely individualistic rather than structurally conditioned (Martin & Zadinsky, 2022; Alabi, 2020).

The Nigerian context intensifies these dynamics considerably. The Nigerian Police Force (NPF) operates under chronic underfunding, poor welfare, and severely strained officer-to-population ratios (Yunusa & Usman, 2022; Amnesty International, 2020; Kokkinos & Vryonidou, 2020). In Oyo Area Command, 265 officers police four local government areas at a ratio of approximately 1:2,500, far exceeding the United Nations-recommended standard of 1:450 (Shane, 2010; Kokkinos & Vryonidou, 2020). Officers face constant redeployments to hostile communities, deep citizen mistrust, and ever-present safety risks, while poor pay, inadequate housing, absent medical insurance, and stalled promotions compound institutional neglect and organizational betrayal, creating conditions under which resentment festers and interpersonal abuse becomes a displaced outlet (Yunusa & Usman, 2022; Amnesty International, 2020; Alabi, 2020).

Occupational stress is widely recognized as a key antecedent of negative workplace behavior. Chronic stressors, including dangerous assignments, excessive workload, hostile citizen interactions, and inadequate welfare, lead to irritability, emotional fatigue, and aggression that manifest as demeaning conduct toward

colleagues (Gershon et al., 2009; Obianuju et al., 2022; Shane, 2019). Junior-ranking officers, who lack autonomy and bear disproportionate frontline burdens, are especially vulnerable to stress-induced loss of self-regulation, making incivility and bullying a coping mechanism as much as a symptom of larger institutional failures (Shane, 2019; Obianuju et al., 2022; Alabi, 2020). Leadership style further shapes interpersonal conduct. Authoritarian leadership, characterized by coercive control and punitive command, is consistently associated with workplace aggression and abusive supervision (Jiang et al., 2017). Importantly, Nigeria's high power-distance cultural context may moderate this relationship: where rigid command is institutionally normalized, officers may perceive authoritarian directives as routine rather than unjust, potentially attenuating any direct link between authoritarian leadership and peer demeaning behaviors (Hofstede, 2011; Alabi, 2020; Yunusa & Usman, 2022).

Perceived organizational injustice constitutes another significant predictor; this variable organisational justice has long been associated with workplace attitudes and behaviours (Fehintola et al., 2026). When officers perceive that promotions, welfare allocations, task assignments, and disciplinary processes are unfair, the resulting resentment and cynicism increase the likelihood of deviant and hostile interpersonal conduct (Reknes et al., 2020). Justice climate theory explains how localized unfairness shapes group norms, making disrespect more tolerated across units over time (Reknes et al., 2020; Vasconcelos, 2020). In contrast, ethical leadership, characterized by fairness, integrity, and genuine concern for subordinates, is associated with reduced bullying and incivility and moderates the corrosive effects of stress by promoting supportive environments (Bedi et al., 2016; Hoch et al., 2018; Brown & Treviño, 2006). However, where institutional mistrust is pervasive, as in contexts shaped by systemic corruption and scarce resources, the protective value of ethical leadership may be diminished and its influence delayed rather than immediate (Brown & Treviño, 2006; Bedi et al., 2016).

This study is grounded in Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1986), particularly reciprocal determinism, which holds that behavior results from the continuous interplay between personal factors, individual actions, and the environmental context. Officers working within hostile, stressful, and structurally unjust environments are more likely to adopt and reproduce demeaning behaviors, as authoritarian leadership models disrespect that subordinates may imitate while organizational injustice breeds cynicism that provides fertile ground for interpersonal abuse (Jiang et al., 2017; Reknes et al., 2020). Despite this theoretical relevance, systematic empirical evidence on the prevalence and predictors of demeaning behaviors within the NPF is still scarce, particularly in semi-urban contexts, and junior-ranking officers remain a neglected group despite their disproportionate exposure to frontline pressures (Alabi, 2020; Amnesty International, 2020; Moffette & Bruckert, 2023). This study addresses these gaps by establishing the prevalence of demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking officers in Oyo Area Command and examining how occupational stress, authoritarian

leadership, perceived organizational injustice, and ethical leadership predict such behaviors within this resource-constrained, high-risk policing context.

2. Research Question and Hypotheses

RQ1: What is the prevalence of demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers in the study context?

H1: Occupational stress will positively predict engagement in demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers.

H2: Authoritarian leadership style will be positively associated with demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers.

H3: Perceived organizational injustice will positively predict demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers.

H4: Ethical leadership will be negatively associated with demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers.

3. Methodology

a. Study Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to investigate the prevalence and predictors of demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers within Oyo Police Area Command. The design was appropriate because it allowed the researcher to collect quantitative data at a single point in time, enabling examination of associations between occupational stress, authoritarian leadership, perceived organizational injustice, ethical leadership, and demeaning behaviors.

b. Study Area

The study was conducted in Oyo Police Area Command, under the Oyo State Police Command. The area command consists of six divisional headquarters: Jobele, Awe, Ojongbodu, Atiba, Oyo, and Ilora divisions. Each division has varying staff strength and rank distribution, reflecting the diverse organizational composition of the Nigeria Police Force at the local command level.

c. Population of the Study

The target population consisted of all sworn officers working within the six divisions under Oyo Area Command. At the time of data collection, the total number of officers across divisions was 248. The rank distribution showed that the majority of officers were Inspectors and Police Constables, with relatively few holding higher supervisory ranks such as CSPs, SPs, or DSPs. Since the study focused on junior-ranking officers, the primary respondents were those occupying positions from Assistant Superintendent of Police (ASP) down to Police Constable (PC). Table 1 presents the distribution of officers by rank and division.

Table 1. Distribution of Police Personnel in Oyo Area Command by Division and Rank

Division	ACP	CSP	SP	DSP	ASP	C. Insp.	Insp.	Sub Insp.	S/ Major	Sgt	Cpl	PC	Total
Jobele	0	0	1	3	6	0	7	0	4	3	3	11	38
Awe	0	1	0	2	5	0	9	0	0	2	2	10	31
Ojongbodu	0	0	2	4	4	0	20	0	3	0	4	17	54
Atiba	0	1	2	1	5	0	15	0	2	1	7	31	65
Oyo	0	1	2	4	6	0	16	0	4	2	4	16	55
Ilorra	0	0	2	1	2	0	4	0	2	1	4	6	22
Total	0	3	9	15	28	0	71	0	15	9	24	91	265

d. Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Due to the operational nature of policing, the study employed a stratified random sampling technique. Each division was treated as a stratum, and proportional allocation was used to determine the number of respondents. A total of 100 officers (Inspectorial cadre and below) was drawn from 265 officers across the six divisions, representing approximately 38 % of the total population. The proportional approach ensured equitable representation across divisions and minimized sampling bias. Table 2 presents the distribution by division and sample allocated.

Table 2. Population and Sample Distribution by Division

Division	Total Population	Sample Size
Jobele	38	15
Awe	31	13
Ojongbodu	54	21
Atiba	65	26
Oyo	55	19
Ilorra	22	6
Total	248	100

e. Procedure

Permission was obtained from the Oyo Area Commander to approach officers within their respective divisions. Trained research assistants distributed self-administered questionnaires to selected participants during routine briefing sessions or after patrol schedules to minimize disruption of duties. Respondents were assured

of confidentiality and encouraged to respond honestly. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately to reduce non-response rates.

f. Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the relevant institutional review board. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were informed of the voluntary nature of participation, their right to withdraw without penalty, and the assurance of anonymity. No personally identifying information was collected. Culturally sensitive modifications were made during pilot testing to ensure measures reflected the local policing context. All procedures adhered to the ethical standards of the American Psychological Association (APA) and the Nigerian National Code of Health Research Ethics.

g. Instrumentation

The study employed a structured questionnaire comprising standardized scales measuring both independent and dependent variables. Each scale was selected for its strong psychometric reputation in organizational psychology research.

Demeaning Behavior Scale: Demeaning behaviors were measured by adapting the Workplace Incivility Scale (WIS) developed by Cortina et al. (2001). The scale consists of 7 items assessing subtle and overt demeaning acts such as disrespect, belittlement, and condescending remarks, rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = never to 5 = very often). Previous studies report Cronbach's alpha values above .85.

Occupational Stress Scale: Occupational stress was measured using the adapted Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10; Cohen et al., 1994), containing 10 items capturing feelings of tension, overload, and unpredictability associated with police work, rated from 0 (never) to 4 (very often). The scale consistently shows alpha coefficients between .78 and .91.

Authoritarian Leadership Scale: The Leader Behavior Description Questionnaire (LBDQ; Stogdill, 1963) was modified to measure perceptions of leadership behavior by subordinates. Following testing, 10 items were extracted and renamed the Authoritarian Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ), assessing the extent to which leaders impose rigid control, discourage autonomy, and prioritize obedience. Prior studies report alpha values of .80 or higher.

Organizational Injustice Scale: The Organizational Justice Scale (Colquitt, 2001) is a 20-item, four-dimensional instrument measuring distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informational justice. The scale demonstrates excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .90-.92$) and strong construct validity across cultures. Pilot testing among Nigerian police officers achieved satisfactory reliability ($\alpha > .80$).

Ethical Leadership Scale: Ethical leadership was assessed using the Ethical Leadership Scale (ELS; Brown et al., 2005), consisting of 10 items evaluating integrity, fairness, role modeling, and concern for subordinates' welfare, rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The ELS demonstrates Cronbach's alpha ranging from .88 to .94 across organizational contexts.

Prior to main data collection, the questionnaire was pilot-tested on 15 officers from a nearby division not included in the final study to assess cultural relevance, clarity, and comprehensibility. Minor modifications were made without altering

conceptual meaning. Reliability analyses confirmed satisfactory Cronbach's alpha values across all scales, exceeding the .70 benchmark, confirming cultural appropriateness and psychometric soundness.

h. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS (Version 27). Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and standard deviations) examined the prevalence of demeaning behaviors. Multiple regression analyses tested the predictive relationships between occupational stress, authoritarian leadership, perceived organizational injustice, ethical leadership, and demeaning behaviors. Pearson's correlation explored bivariate associations. Regression diagnostics checked for multicollinearity, normality, and homoscedasticity. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$.

4. Results

a. Sample Characteristics

A total of 100 junior-ranking police officers participated in the study, drawn from the six divisions under Oyo Command. The sample comprised Inspectors, Sergeants, Corporals, and Police Constables. Higher-ranking administrative officers were excluded due to the study's focus on junior-ranking personnel. The selected sample provided a fair representation of the operational police force in semi-urban Oyo, enabling valid inferences about the prevalence and predictors of demeaning behaviors.

b. Prevalence of Demeaning Behaviors

Analysis of the Workplace Incivility Scale scores revealed that a substantial majority (72 %) of officers reported experiencing demeaning behaviors frequently (sometimes to very often), while 18 % reported occasional experiences and only 10 % reported rarely or never encountering such behaviors.

Table 3. Prevalence Categories of Demeaning Behavior among Junior-Ranking Police Officers

Incivility Level	Mean Score Range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Low (Never/Rarely)	≤ 2.0	10	10 %
Moderate (Occasionally)	2.1 – 3.5	18	18 %
High (Sometimes–Very Often)	≥ 3.6	72	72 %

Note: Demeaning behaviour levels were determined using participants' average scores across the seven items of the adapted Workplace Incivility Scale, rated from 1 = Never to 5 = Very Often.

The results in Table 3 indicate that demeaning behavior is highly prevalent among junior-ranking police officers in the study context. With 72% of officers reporting high levels of frequent disrespectful, dismissive, or belittling conduct, 18% moderate levels, and only 10% low exposure, demeaning behavior emerges as a

widespread and normalized interpersonal dynamic within the policing environment, with significant implications for morale, teamwork, and psychological well-being.

5. Hypothesis Testing

Table 4. Multiple Regression Predicting Demeaning Behaviors

Predictor Variable	β (Beta)	t-value	p-value	Result
Occupational Stress	.42	4.98	< .001	Supported
Authoritarian Leadership Style	.10	1.11	.270	Not Supported
Perceived Organizational Injustice	.37	3.85	< .001	Supported
Ethical Leadership Style	-.08	-0.95	.344	Not Supported

$R^2 = .46$, $Adjusted R^2 = .44$, $F(4,95) = 20.41$, $p < .001$

a. Hypothesis 1 (Occupational Stress)

The regression results indicated that occupational stress was a significant positive predictor of demeaning behaviors ($\beta = .42$, $p < .001$). This suggests that as stress levels among officers increase, so does the likelihood of engaging in demeaning conduct toward colleagues. This finding confirms that the demanding nature of policing, characterized by life-threatening assignments and unpredictable transfers, fuels negative interpersonal behaviors. Officers who endure chronic stress may displace frustrations onto subordinates and peers in the form of belittlement or hostility.

b. Hypothesis 2 (Authoritarian Leadership)

Authoritarian leadership was not found to be a significant predictor ($\beta = .10$, $p = .270$). Although a positive trend was observed, the relationship was not statistically significant. This suggests that while rigid command structures and obedience-based supervision exist in Nigerian policing, they may not directly explain why junior-ranking officers demean one another.

c. Hypothesis 3 (Organizational Injustice)

Perceived organizational injustice significantly predicted demeaning behaviors ($\beta = .37$, $p < .001$). Officers who believed that promotions, task assignments, and disciplinary processes were unfair were more likely to engage in demeaning behaviors. When officers perceive systemic injustice, such as favoritism in promotions or inequitable distribution of resources, they may internalize resentment and express it through demeaning acts toward colleagues.

d. Hypothesis 4 (Ethical Leadership)

Ethical leadership was not a significant predictor of demeaning behaviors ($\beta = -.08$, $p = .344$). Although the relationship was negative, it was statistically insignificant. This indicates that ethical leadership, while conceptually protective, may not yet be robustly embedded in the policing culture of Oyo.

6. Discussion of Findings

The high prevalence of demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers in Oyo (72 % reporting frequent experiences) highlights a deeply entrenched

culture of incivility in the Nigerian police system, exceeding reported rates of 40 to 55 % in some Western policing contexts (Schilpzand et al., 2016). The under-resourced and high-risk environment in which Nigerian officers operate, where hostility from citizens, safety uncertainty, and limited welfare support coexist, collectively normalizes toxic peer interactions. Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1986) offers explanatory insight: officers exposed to stressful and unjust environments may imitate or reproduce similar toxic behaviors, making demeaning conduct a learned coping mechanism and a cultural norm. The structural realities of Oyo Area Command deepen this picture: with approximately 265 officers serving an estimated 500,000 residents across four local government areas, the officer-to-population ratio of 1:2,500 far exceeds the United Nations' recommended 1:450 (Shane, 2010; Kokkinos & Vryonidou, 2020). Extended working hours, poor pay, inadequate accommodation, absent medical insurance, and stalled promotions compound institutional neglect and organizational betrayal, with resentment easily displaced into interpersonal conduct (Yunusa & Usman, 2022; Amnesty International, 2020).

The finding that occupational stress positively predicted demeaning behaviors is consistent with stress-strain and frustration-aggression models (Onyemah et al., 2024; Hershcovis & Barling, 2017). In Oyo, stressors are magnified by poor equipment, lack of community trust, and the possibility of fatal encounters, spilling over into interpersonal relationships in the form of belittling, disrespect, and other demeaning conduct. Officers under chronic stress may have reduced emotional regulation capacities, increasing the likelihood of lashing out at colleagues (Garbarino et al., 2013), making stress management interventions critical for reducing toxic workplace climates.

Contrary to expectations, authoritarian leadership was not a significant predictor of demeaning behavior. Unlike Western contexts where authoritarian leadership is associated with workplace incivility (Welbourne et al., 2015), in Nigerian policing it is deeply institutionalized and culturally normalized. Officers may interpret rigid command and obedience structures as inherent to policing's professional identity rather than as unjust. This aligns with Hofstede's cultural dimension theory, which identifies Nigeria as a high power-distance society where hierarchical authority is widely accepted (Odotayo & Adewuyi, 2024; Hofstede, 2011). Authoritarian leadership may thus not directly predict toxic peer behavior, though it may indirectly reinforce stress and injustice. This finding underscores the importance of cultural relativism in organizational behavior research.

The strong predictive effect of organizational injustice confirms that fairness perceptions are a core determinant of workplace conduct (Colquitt, 2001). In semi-urban Nigerian policing, the scarcity of resources, opaque promotion processes, inequitable welfare allocation, and arbitrary transfers exacerbate injustice perceptions that in turn fuel hostility among peers. Although ethical leadership was negatively associated with demeaning behavior, the relationship was statistically insignificant, suggesting that ethical leadership is not yet systematically institutionalized in the Nigerian policing context but remains dependent on

individual leader dispositions. In environments dominated by authoritarian traditions and systemic injustice, ethical leadership may be too fragile to counteract entrenched toxic norms, and its protective role may be more long-term in character (Brown & Treviño, 2006; Bedi et al., 2016).

7. Conclusion

This study investigated the prevalence and predictors of demeaning behaviors among junior-ranking police officers in Oyo, a semi-urban Nigerian policing context. The findings reveal a high prevalence of demeaning behavior, with occupational stress and perceived organizational injustice emerging as significant predictors. Contrary to expectations, authoritarian leadership did not significantly predict demeaning behaviors, suggesting that cultural normalization of hierarchy moderates its impact. Similarly, ethical leadership, though negatively associated with demeaning behaviors, did not exert a significant protective influence. Collectively, these results highlight the unique interplay between stress, fairness perceptions, and cultural norms in shaping workplace mistreatment among police officers. By bringing attention to the neglected issue of intra-police demeaning behavior, this study contributes to filling a critical gap in both organizational and policing literature.

8. Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study relied on self-report measures, which may be subject to social desirability bias; future research could integrate multi-source data, including peer or supervisor ratings, to enhance validity. Second, the cross-sectional design limits causal inference; longitudinal studies would better illuminate how stress, injustice, and leadership dynamics evolve over time and shape demeaning behaviors. Third, the study was conducted within a single area command, and findings may not be generalizable to urban or more resource-endowed Nigerian police commands. Future research should replicate the study across diverse policing contexts to establish broader applicability.

9. Recommendations

Based on the findings, several practical recommendations are proposed. Stress management programs should be established within police divisions through routine counseling, resilience training, and peer-support systems to mitigate the effects of occupational stress on interpersonal conduct. Clear policies for promotions, postings, and welfare distribution should be developed to reduce perceptions of injustice and foster greater organizational transparency. More officers should be recruited to bring officer-to-population ratios closer to international standards, thereby reducing workload-related stress among existing personnel. Investment in welfare packages, including healthcare, housing, and risk allowances, is critical to improving morale and reducing the resentment that fuels demeaning behavior. While authoritarian leadership is normalized in Nigerian policing, leadership development programs should gradually emphasize participatory and ethical leadership practices to reshape

organizational culture over time. Finally, trust between officers and local communities should be built through sustained outreach and dialogue, reducing the external hostility that indirectly fuels internal workplace mistreatment.

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Availability of Data Statement

Upon reasonable request, the corresponding author will provide the datasets created and examined during the current study. Interested readers may contact the corresponding author at adewuyihabeeb@gmail.com for further details, clarification, or access to supplemental materials.

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